

The identification of marine biotechnology value chains with the highest potential for the Mediterranean region

Ana Rotter ^{1,*}, Antonia Giannakourou ², Jesús E. Argente García ³, Grazia Marina Quero ⁴, Charlene Auregan ⁵, George Triantaphyllidis ², Amalia Venetsanopoulou ², Roberta De Carolis ⁶, Chrysa Efstratiou ², Marina Aboal ³, María Ángeles Esteban Abad ³, Ernesta Grigalionyte-Bembic ¹, Yannis Kotzamanis ², Mate Kovač ⁷, Maja Ljubić Čmelar ⁷, Gian Marco Luna ⁴, Cristóbal Aguilera ⁸, Francisco Gabriel Acién Fernández ⁹, Juan Luis Gómez Pinchetti ¹⁰, Sonia Manzo ⁶, Iva Milašincić ⁷, Antun Nadarnija ⁷, Luisa Parrella ⁶, Massimiliano Pinat ⁴, Efstratios Roussos ², Colin Ruel ⁵, Elisabetta Salvatori ⁶, Francisco Javier Sánchez Vázquez ³, María Semitiel García ³, Antonio F. Skarmeta Gómez ³, Jan Ulčar ¹, and Cristian Chiavetta ⁶

- ¹ Marine Biology Station Piran, National Institute of Biology, Fornače 41, 6330 Piran, Slovenia; ana.rotter@nib.si, ernesta.grigalionyte-bembic@nib.si, jan.ulcar@nib.si
 - ² Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Oceanography, 46.7 km Athens-Sounio Avenue, PO Box 712, GR 19013 Anavyssos, Attica, Greece; agiannak@hcmr.gr, ch.efstra@hcmr.gr, avenetsanopoulou@hcmr.gr; Institute of Marine Biology, Biotechnology and Aquaculture, 46.7 km Athens-Sounio Avenue, PO Box 712, GR 19013 Anavyssos, Attica, Greece; jokotz@hcmr.gr, e.roussos@hcmr.gr, gvtrianta@hcmr.gr
 - ³ University of Murcia, Avda. Teniente Flomesta, S/N. 30003 Murcia, Spain; jesus.argente@um.es, skarmeta@um.es, maboal@um.es, aesteban@um.es, mariase@um.es, javisan@um.es
 - ⁴ CNR IRBIM, National Research Council – Institute of Marine Biological Resources and Biotechnologies, Largo Fiera della Pesca, 60125 Ancona, Italy; grazia.quero@irbim.cnr.it, direttore@irbim.cnr.it, massimiliano.pinat@irbim.cnr.it
 - ⁵ Pôle Mer Méditerranée, Toulon Var Technologies, 93 forum de la Méditerranée, 83190 Ollioules, France; auregan.charlene@outlook.com, ruel@polemermediterranee.com
 - ⁶ ENEA, Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, Department for Sustainability; R.C. Casaccia, Via Anguillarese, 301, 00123 S. Maria di Galeria, Rome, Italy; roberta.decarolis@enea.it, elisabetta.salvatori@enea.it; R.C. Portici, P.le Enrico Fermi, 1. 80055 Portici, Naples, Italy; sonia.manzo@enea.it, luisa.parrella@enea.it; R.C. Bologna, Via Martiri di Monte Sole, 4 - 40129 Bologna, Italy; cristian.chiavetta@enea.it
 - ⁷ Croatian Agency for SMEs, Innovations and Investments – HAMAG-BICRO, Ksaver 208, 10000 Zagreb, Croatia; maja.ljubiccmelar@hamagbicro.hr, mate.kovac@hamagbicro.hr, iva.milasincic@hamagbicro.hr, antun.nadramija@hamagbicro.hr
 - ⁸ Institute of Agri Food Research and Technology, Crta. Poble Nou Km 5,5 43540-La Ràpita, Tarragona, Spain; cristobal.aguilera@irta.cat
 - ⁹ University of Almeria CIESOL, Cañada San Urbano S/N, 04120, Almeria, Spain; facien@ual.es
 - ¹⁰ Spanish Bank of Algae, Institute of Oceanography and Global Change, University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, Spain; juan.gomez@ulpgc.es
- * Correspondence: ana.rotter@nib.si

Citation: Lastname, F.; Lastname, F.; Lastname, F. Title. *Mar. Drugs* **2022**, *20*, x. <https://doi.org/10.3390/xxxxx>

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Publisher's Note: MDPI stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: © 2022 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Abstract: Marine (blue) biotechnology is an emerging field enabling valorization of new products and processes with massive potential for innovation and economic growth in the Mediterranean region. However, the innovation potential in this region is not exploited as well as in other European regions due to the lack of a clear identification of the different value chains and high fragmentation of business innovation initiatives. As a result, several opportunities to create an innovative society are being missed. To address this problem, eight Mediterranean countries (Croatia, France, Greece, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) established five national blue biotechnology hubs to identify and address the bottlenecks that prevent the development of marine biotechnology in the region. Following a three-step approach (1. Analysis: setting the scene; 2. Transfer: identification of promising value chains; 3. Capitalization: community creation) we identified three value chains that are most promising for the Mediterranean region: algae production for added-value compounds, integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) and valorization aquaculture/fisheries/processing by-products, unavoidable/unwanted catches and discards. The potential for development of technical and non-technical skills that are necessary to advance in this exciting field is provided

through several stakeholder events which proportioned valuable insight and feedback that should be addressed for marine biotechnology in the Mediterranean region to reach its full potential.

Keywords: marine biotechnology; blue biotechnology; innovation; value chains; Mediterranean; microalgae; macroalgae; IMTA; circular economy, discards valorization.

1. Introduction

To cope with an increasing global population, rapid depletion of many resources, increasing environmental pressures, climate change and as a consequence of the social and cultural changes that are taking place in consumers, Europe needs to radically change its approach to production, consumption, processing, storage, recycling and disposal of biological resources [1]. Therefore, it is necessary to shift the focus to novel sources to develop new products and processes. In this regard, the marine environment, which is vast, largely underexplored and unexploited, represents the opportunity to valorize marine resources [2]. This is done through marine biotechnology, a sector that explores the marine bio-resources (marine organisms and ecosystems) as potential source of innovation and major factor of economic growth, thus representing a significant contributor to the blue bioeconomy. This is also endorsed by the European Commission that is supporting the development of marine-related economic and innovation activities, in particular since the adoption of the Communication on Blue Growth in 2011 when blue economy was adopted as a central element of the European Union's (EU) Integrated Maritime Policy in implementing the Europe 2020 strategy for sustainable and inclusive growth [3]. Recently, the European Commission has published a communication aimed to integrate ocean policy into Europe's new economic policy to ensure that the 'blue economy' plays a major role in the implementation of the European Green Deal (EGD), clearly stating that the dualism between environmental protection and economy must be overcome [4]. The biotechnology sector in the EU directly and indirectly creates 1 million jobs, has a gross added value of 78.7 billion € and is expected to grow globally by at least 50% by 2030 [5,6]. Marine biotechnology solutions, coupled with circular economy business models, are excellent tools for closing production cycles and ensure resource-efficient processes, avoiding waste and keeping resources in use for as long as possible through cascading biomass use and recycling, generating added value products in numerous contexts while ensuring at the same time the protection of natural capital in the ocean.

The Mediterranean Basin, located across the South of Europe and the North of Africa, is unique by virtue of its history, cultural heritage climate, diet, ecosystems, and being a global hotspot of biological diversity [7–9]. In theory, this offers a natural opportunity to advance in the marine biotechnology and the blue bioeconomy sectors. However, in practice, the Mediterranean region has been showing a slower economic growth and employment performance than other middle-income countries, mostly linked to its poor business environment, complicated, ambiguous and often excessive bureaucracy, inadequate production systems, competitiveness and technological transfers [10,11]. This is unfortunate, as Southern European countries (including the Mediterranean region) have excellent education systems and research expertise, but relatively modest funded research bases, lower investment into infrastructures, little and/or fragmented bio-businesses [6]. Moreover, there is Mediterranean fragmentation at regional/national level (in policies, legislation and business initiatives). As marine biotechnology is a relatively young discipline, its key players are not clearly identified at (inter)national levels and the lack of coordination on the key enablers limits its huge growth potential in the region. Therefore, the creation of national, regional and international collaborative networks can establish critical mass, provide a platform for knowledge transfer, facilitate political and financial support, and produce the most creative and innovative results to address important societal challenges [6,12]. Significantly, the establishment of collaborative efforts necessarily relies on teamwork, with a transdisciplinary combination of experts with technical and non-technical

skills, such as social, communication, technology transfer, entrepreneurship, legal, intellectual property protection, business strategy and market research, among others [13,14].

With this in mind, the B-Blue project – “Building the blue biotechnology community in the Mediterranean”, financed through the Interreg Mediterranean Programme between September 2020 and September 2022 (<https://b-blue.interreg-med.eu/>), triggered the creation of a collaborative network, composed of 10 partners from 8 Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) aiming to identify promising marine biotechnology value chains and thus unlock the innovation potential of the region.

A value chain consists of a range of activities required to bring a product from its inception to its end consumer, through a series of steps involving physical transformation and input of various producer services, and disposal after use [15]. Marine biotechnology value chains are tailored to various application sectors, all stemming from a generalized pipeline. It is composed of four basic steps: (i) basic research – bioprospecting, harvesting and collection of available biomass, either the whole organism, its parts or its microbiome. This is followed by (ii) applied research – collection/harvesting of biomass, preservation in culture collections or biobanks, cultivation and biomass processing, extraction, purification, structure elucidation and characterization of natural products, including laboratory scale applications to optimize the production conditions, (iii) industrial scale-up phase to sustain the production quantities and (iv) commercial applications [13]. Different stakeholders from different organizations are typically involved in various stages of value chains and are faced with several challenges, especially the supply, technology development and definition of market needs [16].

Through a series of events, organized in the eight Mediterranean countries within the frame of the B-Blue project, valuable interactions and feedback were sought from relevant and transversal stakeholders from the region, resulting in the identification of the most relevant value chains to be addressed in each territory. The remainder of the article presents the three-step strategy and the results obtained to highlight their potential to assist the growth of marine biotechnology in the Mediterranean region in the next future.

2. Results

To develop the most promising marine biotechnology value chains for the Mediterranean region, project partners, who are internationally renowned experts in either (i) marine biotechnology domain, (ii) provide non-technical skills or (iii) both, conducted the work in a three-step process: analyze-transfer-capitalize. (1) The analysis step consisted of jointly agreeing on the requirements that are mostly important for advancing the marine biotechnology sector. (2) The transfer step enabled to identify the most promising marine biotechnology value chains for the Mediterranean region. (3) The capitalization step provided tools to establish national blue biotechnology hubs.

2.1. Step 1: Analysis. Setting the scene: Fundamental requirements to advance in marine biotechnology in the Mediterranean region

Out of the 81 potential activities that were identified by the Blue Bioeconomy Forum [17] as important for advancing in the field of marine biotechnology and were identified, three were most often selected by expert respondents – project partners from 8 Mediterranean countries, as being the most important. These can be represented as three specific action points: legislation, financing, and collaboration through knowledge creation. More specifically, the three identified requirements that received most votes from the experts and need to be addressed to enable the launch of the value chains were: (i) Highlight marine biotechnology in Smart Specialization Strategies; (ii) Increase funding at national level to support the continuation of projects after their first financing round; and (iii) Bridge the collaboration gap between research and industry by education, training and coaching.

2.2. Step 2: Transfer. Identification of most promising value chains in the Mediterranean region

We first identified the existing good practices that are in development, already implemented or ready to enter the market, pilot actions and research results of innovative solutions in the marine biotechnology sector. This exercise enabled to highlight the innovation potential in the marine biotechnology field and define the value chains that are of strategic importance to capitalize the needs and expertise in the Mediterranean countries, as well as those with high market potential. 90 good practices involved at least one of the project partners' countries (the Mediterranean countries of Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain). These individual good practices focused on 149 thematic areas (considering that one best practice can cover multiple areas) and are shown in Figure 1. Among these, 55 good practices deal with a specific group of organisms (Figure 2), while the rest are either of a strategic nature, or are not specific for any particular organism type. The full list of good practices is available as Supplementary Table 1.

Figure 1. Number of good practice examples of marine biotechnology value chains that tackled a specific thematic area in the eight Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain). Note: most of these good practices involve the participation of international consortia with countries that are also outside the Mediterranean region. Nevertheless, at least one partner is from the aforementioned countries.

Figure 2. Number of good practices that target any of the four organism type categories in the assessed good practices among the existing marine biotechnology value chains that are developed within any of the eight Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain). Note: most of these good practices involve the participation of international consortia with countries that are also outside the Mediterranean region. Nevertheless, at least one partner is from the aforementioned countries.

2.3. Step 3: Capitalization. Creation of the community by establishment of blue biotechnology hubs

To capitalize the existing knowledge and prevent its loss that typically occurs after the end of financing rounds, we first conducted a stakeholder mapping exercise. 636 potentially interested stakeholders from several sectors and activities (administration, research and academia, industry and small/medium enterprises (SMEs), non-governmental organizations (NGOs), past and current projects, media) from eight Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) were identified. These stakeholders are important to establish national communities of practice. We followed the living labs approach that enables the co-creation of innovative user-oriented solutions. The creation of living labs was selected as they provide a resource for collective innovation for new products, processes, and services [18]. In B-Blue project we call them “Blue Biotechnology Hubs (BBt Hubs)”. Five selected Mediterranean territories established these hubs – France, Greece, Italy, Slovenia and Spain. They were designed to be open to different stakeholders to allow them to co-create new knowledge and solutions. Through several types of setups (almost 40 events organized: workshops, networking events, work cafés, hackathons and strategic meetings), we addressed over 1,500 individuals that are directly or indirectly involved in, or can contribute to developing marine biotechnology value chains in the Mediterranean region.

3. Discussion

We followed a three-step approach to define the value chains with most potential in the Mediterranean region: (1) analysis – (2) transfer – (3) capitalization. By analyzing the existing initiatives and good practice examples, we first created the knowledge repository on a national level. This also enabled to identify/confirm the bottlenecks in the Mediterranean region (as presented in the Introduction section): lack of identified experts, high fragmentation of activities, where research and innovation are often developed as isolated initiatives without coordination activities, which could ease the access to the market. We follow with the discussion on each of the three steps and detail our approach to identify, create and capitalize knowledge on the value chains with most potential in the Mediterranean region.

3.1. Step 1: Analysis – identification of bottlenecks

The identified bottlenecks that call for specific requirements to set the scene for advancing innovation in the field of marine biotechnology in the Mediterranean region can broadly be clustered in three categories: legislation and policy support, financing, collaboration through knowledge creation.

3.1.1. Policy support

European policies. Within the EU, the blue economy is expected to play a major role in the long-term strategy to reach the full transformation toward a sustainable growth stated by the EGD, that will build on targets such as carbon neutrality, circular economy, zero pollution and the restoration of biodiversity [19]. The Mediterranean Sea, being a strategic crossroad for the history, economy and culture of Europe, Middle East and North African countries, will be central for this transformation [20]. When dealing with seafood, for example, wild fisheries, today representing the main source of food from the oceans, have made in the last years in the EU considerable efforts to bring fish stocks back to sustainable levels and to reduce overfishing to meet the Common Fisheries Policy and its standards. Aquaculture has the potential to be an alternative source of sustainable seafood and to further become a large source of low-impact food. However, the positioning of mariculture as a seafood fix as compared to wild-capture fisheries still has to be fully established [21], in light of the numerous challenges to be addressed in order to also fully meet the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to operate under a One Health Perspective [22]. Aquaculture will need to develop more research and innovation including testing of new sustainable sources of food and feed, developing new marketing standards, and promote decarbonization and circular economy practices, while facilitating its coexistence with other sectors of the blue economy. In this sense, the recently launched large-scale investment by Horizon Europe in research (EU Mission on Oceans and Waters “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”) including its Partnership “A climate neutral, sustainable and productive Blue Economy” (in brief “Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership” or SBEP), the new European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) and others will certainly boost innovation and advancing of this sector, and foster the transformative change required to achieve a transition of the blue economy that will benefit the planet, people and economy. Furthermore the Strategic EU Blue Economy partnership supports actions towards the ocean dimensions of sustainable development in the context of the UN 2030 Agenda with its three pillars namely sustainability, climate neutrality and productivity.

Regional policies. Following the Conference on “Strengthening Euro-Mediterranean Cooperation through Research and Innovation” held in La Valletta in 2017, under the auspices of the Maltese Presidency of the Council of the EU, La Valletta Declaration was released. The Declaration restates the belief that strengthening Euro-Mediterranean cooperation in research and innovation contributes to fully tapping the potential of economic growth and sustainable development of the Mediterranean region and commits to knowledge creation and identification of innovative solutions. In addition, the BLUEMED initiative (<http://www.bluedmed-initiative.eu/>) has been a lighthouse in the Mediterranean

region, aiming to advance a shared vision for a healthier, more productive, resilient, better known and valued Mediterranean Sea, promoting the citizens' social well-being and prosperity, and boosting economic growth and jobs. The BLUEMED Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda which was updated in 2018 outlines a set of key challenges for the Mediterranean region including different sectors of interest such as ecosystems, climate change, biotechnologies, aquaculture, fisheries, observing systems, offshore platforms, spatial planning.

National policies. The smart specialization strategy (S3) has presented a profound structural revolution in the way innovation policies are conceived by identifying local potentials, local needs and advocating between investments in knowledge and human capital, and the present industrial and technological 'vocations' and competences of territories [23]. It facilitates regional and national diversified and decentralized specialization into areas that should secure existing and future competitiveness, thus pivoting to regional innovation [24,25]. Indeed, the S3 should prioritize domains, areas and economic activities where regions or countries have a competitive advantage or have the potential to generate knowledge-driven growth and to bring about the economic transformation needed to tackle the major and most urgent challenges for the society and the natural and built environment. Importantly, although an initial set of priorities is identified during the first design of the smart specialization strategy, they can be changed or modified when new information/developments makes it advisable. Hence, it comes to no surprise that several Mediterranean experts identified the possibility of participating in the national S3 as a window of opportunity for providing feedback and positioning themselves as national experts, resource and knowledge providers, thus creating actual impact and changing the policy content. For example, during the period of the project implementation, the national S3 for most Mediterranean countries were in their upgrade period, thus providing the opportunity to include sustainable blue economy as an important horizontal area that is well integrated to other national priority areas.

3.1.2. Increase funding at national level

Once the policy support is achieved, other pressing issues for bringing the marine biotechnology (blue) products to the market are addressed, for example: increased funding at the national level to support the continuation of development of marine biotechnology products and processes, also through engagement of the industry sector in research and development. Nationally, measures need to be developed to incentivize researchers/companies to collaborate in blue economy sectors. These funding tools can be split into two main categories. Firstly, the public support for investments in industrial research and development (R&D) activities, which then also include collaboration between universities and industry, including SMEs, and secondly, the matching funds for non-research investments in marine biotechnology sector to advance the non-technical skills. Existing good practice examples include the Innovation in the fisheries and aquaculture service, a service offered by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food of the government of Spain, with public access to relevant information related to innovation in the fisheries and aquaculture sector such as R&D strategic plan, map of technological platforms and capacity maps. Additionally, the Spanish PLEAMAR Programme of the Ministry of Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge and implemented through the Biodiversity Foundation aims to support the fishing and aquaculture sector through annual grants in its commitment to sustainability and to the protection and conservation of biodiversity and natural heritage.

3.1.3. Education, training, mentoring and coaching

Besides reaching a policy consensus and enabling financial support, it is imperative to provide adequate opportunities for human capital development. This can be done at two levels, either before (i.e., during formal education) or after entering the workforce. Partners have selected several useful activities for the knowledge development in the field of marine biotechnology. (i) Designing mentorship/coaching activities on technical and

non-technical skills, where skilled individuals (coaches, mentors) support clients (at any career level) by providing formal and informal training and guidance. Coaching is more focused on performance and specific tasks or objectives, while mentoring provides a more generalized support. Establishing mentoring or coaching programs provide benefits to mentors, protégés, and organizations, but not all organizations have such programs in place [26]. When these coaching activities are coupled with networking opportunities, the results can yield to increase in all stages of marine biotechnology value chain, from knowledge acquisition and participation in innovative collaboration networks to economic benefits [12,27] (ii) Providing start-ups in the sector with advice on business and financing. An example are business incubators that offer either training, support or work-space. Another example are seed accelerators, typically targeting existing companies and/or products or processes that are in higher stages of technology readiness. (iii) Developing targeted workshops and trainings on cooperation between the blue bioeconomy sector and universities. (iv) Assisting local marine biotechnology producers: for example, creating taste labs, school campaigns and education classes. (v) Designing Mediterranean-based international study programs on bachelor's and PhD levels with scholarships. Good practice examples in the Mediterranean region include two projects. The first one is DEEP BLUE (Developing Education and Employment Partnerships for a Sustainable Blue Growth in the Western Mediterranean Region), which was financed by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF). The second project is the BlueSkills (Blue Jobs and Responsible Growth in the Mediterranean) regional project, endorsed by the Union for the Mediterranean and aiming to promote blue employment by developing skills, exchanging knowledge and valorizing research for a more sustainable Mediterranean Sea. However, since these good practices depend on the financing scheme and are time-constricted by the duration of individual projects, the sustainability and longevity of marine biotechnology/bioeconomy (blue) education in the Mediterranean region needs to be considered in the next future, possibly by iterating the current national educational curricula, especially the tertiary level ones that provide most in-depth specialization opportunities.

3.2. Step 2: Transfer – promising value chains in the Mediterranean region

After assessing the Mediterranean good practices benchmarking exercise (Figure 1 and 2) we defined the value chains that are currently best represented in the Mediterranean region. Algae (macro- and microalgae) production to obtain added-value compounds, represented in almost 60% of the target organisms (Figure 2) and aquaculture or fisheries discard valorization, that was represented in over 26% of the best practice sectors (Figure 1), were on top of the best practice lists. We therefore focus on these sectors as the ones with highest potential for advancing the innovation status in the Mediterranean region. We further categorized the aquaculture sector (Figure 1) into two emerging value chains: IMTA and valorization of aquaculture/fisheries/processing by-products Category 3, unavoidable/unwanted catches and discards. Taken together with algal biotechnology (Figure 2), these are the three most promising value chains with high relevance for the Mediterranean region. They are discussed in the subparagraphs below.

3.2.1. Algae production for added-value compounds

In the ambitious strategy for developing the bioeconomy in Europe, algae represent an emerging biological resource of great importance for its potential applications in different fields. They have biosorption potential, can sequester atmospheric CO₂, provide biofuel, feed and food supplements, food ingredients, nutraceuticals, and cosmetics, among others [13]. The global production of macroalgae amounts up to 35 million tons (Mt) of fresh weight annually (where 97% of its biomass derives from aquaculture and the rest is harvested) and around 24% and less than 1% of it is contributed within the EU for harvesting and aquaculture, respectively [28]. The global production is still primarily dominated by two Asian countries, namely China and Indonesia, producing together >90% of the global market supply [29]. Hence, although Europe production is currently small-scale, the macroalgal sector is considered as the most notable subsector in European

blue bioeconomy and the projections imply an expansion in European annual production from around 0.3 Mt up to 8 Mt by 2030 which could create up to 85,000 jobs [19,30]. It is estimated that the key seaweeds grown in the Mediterranean countries (including their Atlantic coasts) in 2030 could include for instance sea lettuce (*Ulva lactuca*) for human consumption, sugar kelp (*Saccharina latissima*) for use in food products and animal feed, dulse (*Palmaria palmata*) for the food and cosmetics sectors, *Asparagopsis taxiformis* for cattle feed additives with methane-reducing properties, and oarweed (*Laminaria digitata*) to produce alginate for use in the food additives and biopackaging segments [30]. An emerging field is also the seaweed farming for ecological restoration of marine macroalgal forests, given the predicted upscaling from small-scale, short-term academic experiments to industry and restoration practitioners, required to secure the oceans' sustainable future [31] and building up in the Mediterranean region on the knowledge produced by successful projects such as AFRIMED (<http://afrimed-project.eu/>) and ROCPOP-life (<http://www.rocpoplife.eu/>). Regardless on the target value chain, however, it is important to use the basic ecological knowledge of these species and avoid their introduction into new areas, especially where they might be considered invasive, such as is the case for some *Asparagopsis* species [32].

In the Mediterranean countries (Portugal is included) there are currently 280 companies producing algae found through European Marine Observation and Data Network – EMODnet [33] and through the project partners from Mediterranean countries. The produced organisms by companies from different Mediterranean countries within the B-Blur project are shown in Figure 3. The figure includes the genus *Arthrospira* (*Spirulina*) as well, as this cyanobacterium is widely used for industrial production due to their biocompounds content, including biopeptides, biopolymers, pigments, carbohydrates, essential fatty acids, minerals, oligoelements, and sterols [34]. The taxonomic classification of *Spirulina* either into cyanobacteria or algae is an ongoing discussion in the scientific community [35] and is beyond the scope of this work, hence, it is represented as a standalone taxon to avoid any confusion. Their widespread production is also clearly seen in the Mediterranean region, with France owning the majority (72%) of companies specialized in the cultivation of this cyanobacterium. Microalgae and macroalgae have fewer producer companies. Interestingly, macroalgae are produced in only three of the B-Blue Mediterranean countries (France, Spain and Portugal). The official data have no records about microalgae cultivation in Greece, Slovenia and Croatia. However, Greece has proven experience and capacity in microalgae cultivation of the species *Isochrysis* sp., *Chlorella* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Rhodomonas* sp., *Dunaliella* sp. at industrial scale, as part of the daily routine of several hatcheries, which support larvae feeding in fish farms. Croatia has an enterprise in microalgae cultivation (hatchery) and Slovenia reports 3 enterprises in the last 5 years producing small quantities of microalgae and *Spirulina*.

Figure 3. Registered companies in B-Blue countries that produce macroalgae, microalgae and *Spirulina*.

Macroalgal species which are mostly produced in B-Blue countries are presented in Figure 4. Although macroalgae production at a commercial scale is recorded only in three B-Blue countries, other B-Blue countries (such as Greece and Italy) are cultivating macroalgae at a pilot scale as part of several research programs (aquaculture in open tanks and small aquariums). Many edible macroalgae have high nutritional values and the environmentally friendly cultivation and harvesting methods make them appealing as raw material for food and feed [36–38].

Over 70% of registered macroalgal production in Mediterranean countries is attributed to harvesting, mostly manual, which faces the challenge of balancing the socio-economic and environmental sustainability of the activity [39]. It is therefore of strategic importance to promote macroalgal aquaculture, which on one hand presents a higher potential for scaling up the production volumes, while on the other one being associated with high infrastructural and operational costs [39]. Seaweed farming is often considered as the least environmentally damaging form of aquaculture and has been shown to have positive effects on many ecosystem services [40]. The species commercially harvested are primarily *Laminaria hyperborea*, *Ascophyllum nodosum*, *Fucus* sp., *Himantalia elongata*, *Porphyra* sp. and *Undaria* sp. [41], while *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria* sp., *Palmaria palmata*, *Chondrus crispus* and *Ulva* sp. are the species mainly cultivated [36]. Seaweed production (both harvesting from wild stocks and aquaculture) is primarily concentrated in the Atlantic region with few units cultivating species that are native in the Mediterranean Sea e.g., *Ulva* sp., *Gracilaria* sp. [39]. Mechanical harvesting is undertaken by boats and is mainly practiced in France (Brittany), Spain (Galicia and Asturias) and to a lesser degree in the Basque country (France). Manual harvesting of macroalgae and gathering of storm cast macroalgae are important in France, Spain and Portugal [42]. Harvesters either gather the cast or cut macroalgae at low tide. Diving is another way to harvest macroalgae manually and is practiced mostly in Portugal [42]. Macroalgae are cultivated in land-based tanks or ponds or in sea-based (coastal and offshore) structures such as long-lines or rafts [43]. They can be cultivated as a monoculture or IMTA, which is further discussed in the

next subchapter. However, the quantities of cultivated European macroalgae are insufficient in volume, too expensive and produced by a fragmented supply chain, concentrated in the Atlantic area. This represents an opportunity for the Mediterranean region to promote the development of this exciting sector in this region, providing that careful attention is placed also on the environmental factors (such as the difference in water temperature between the Atlantic and the Mediterranean waters). Currently, no Mediterranean species is being grown and the efforts should be focused in the search of autochthonous species (by definition perfectly adapted to the environmental conditions). So far only a few companies have managed to secure a license for large-scale operations and leverage sufficient funding to expand. The demand for “all-natural ingredients” has been on the rise, owing to the safety concerns associated with synthetic ingredients; hence, the demand for macroalgal protein-based products is expected to grow considerably in the coming years.

Figure 4. Macroalgal species that are most often cultivated in the B-Blue countries by registered companies. Different colors denote the producer countries.

The microalgal species (freshwater and marine species) that are most often cultivated in the B-Blue countries are presented in Figure 5. Some are used for in the food industry, such as the green algae *Chlorella sp.*, which is internationally identified as “Generally Recognized As Safe” (GRAS), a certification legislated under the United States Food and Drug Administration – FDA [44]. Some species of these microalgae are also included under the EU Novel food regulation. Other certified GRAS species include the green algae *Haematococcus sp.* and *Dunaliella sp.* [44]. Microalgae are also used in the aquaculture feed sector and as feed ingredients for livestock [45,46]. When introducing algae in aquafeeds, the results show an improvement in the health of the fish due to the probiotic compounds contained into the microalgal biomass [47]. The microalgal biotechnology industry is of high interest due to the availability of multiple high-value products such as pigments, carbohydrates, proteins, nutraceuticals, biopharmaceuticals for a broad variety of applications [48]. However, the bulk production of microalgae carbohydrates and proteins for the food and feed sector has not yet grown in accordance with its potential, because it requires higher production volumes and consequently the boosting of the cost-effective scale-up [49–51]. Moreover, the prices are not yet comparable with cheaper land-based

alternatives, such as soy protein and palm oil. Nevertheless, the development of technology keeps boosting the development and cost and technology optimizations for microalgal applications. Microalgae are cultivated using different production systems. (i) Photobioreactors, commonly (71%) used for microalgae production in Europe, are generally capital intensive allowing a stricter control of the environmental factors and biomass quality as well as an increase in the photosynthetic efficiency and productivity [52,53]. (ii) Open ponds entail a lower investment but have a high risk of contamination, lower control of the environmental conditions and greater land and water requirements [54,55]. (iii) Finally, fermenters refer only to heterotrophic algae. Large-scale cultivation will decisively contribute to the development of a sustainable industry for biomass production as well as generate cost-effective high-value products. Indeed, the development of suitable and cost-effective biomass processing and harvesting strategies that contribute to around 30% of the final biomass cost, is still ongoing [48,56].

Figure 5. Microalgal species that are most often cultivated in the B-Blue partner countries by registered companies. Different colors denote the producer countries.

3.2.2. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture – IMTA

Animal aquaculture is one of the fastest growing food production sectors that has been generating concerning consequences for the environment, including chemical and biological pollution, disease outbreaks, unsustainable feeds and competition for coastal space [57,58]. To promote sustainable approaches, IMTA systems combine fed aquaculture species with inorganic extractive species (e.g., macroalgae) and organic extractive species (e.g., suspension- and deposit-feeders) cultivated in proximity [59]. Finfish, macroalgae, mollusks, crustaceans, sea cucumbers, sea urchins, sponges, polychaetes and plants (such as *Salicornia europaea* and *Aster tripolium*) have all been identified to have a high potential for inclusion in efficient IMTA [60–64]. Through IMTA, some of the uneaten feed and wastes, nutrients, and by-products, considered “lost” from the fed component, are recaptured and converted into harvestable and healthy seafood of commercial value [65]. These systems significantly contribute to the sustainability of aquaculture through economic, societal and environmental benefits, including the recycling of waste nutrients from higher trophic-level species into production of lower trophic-level species, thus increasing production efficiency, product and economic diversification and social accepta-

bility of farmed products [59,60]. In addition, biomass produced in IMTA systems, including those from macroalgae, bivalve shells or other type of wastes, can be further exploited for other (blue and green) biotechnological applications. Hence, the development of IMTA value chains can significantly contribute to the establishment of circularity in aquaculture where waste streams from one industry provide the raw materials for another. At the same time, IMTA has the potential to reduce the nutrients and organic matter inputs from finfish aquaculture, thus having a significant environmental impact of fish farms, while creating appropriate business models to increase profitability. Furthermore, this concept aligns with recommendations made in the Food from the Oceans report (2017), which highlighted the need to expand low- and multi-trophic marine aquaculture as an ecologically efficient source of increasing food and feed [66].

The efforts to implement IMTA on a large scale are mainly concentrated in the Atlantic area and North Europe and only trials carried out at experimental/laboratory scale exist in the Mediterranean region [60,62,64]. Currently, IMTA has several important challenges. There is a need to address and estimate the potential for contaminants in uneaten feed and feces to bioaccumulate by organic extractive and inorganic extractive species, potentially reentering the food chain supply [67]. Similarly, current legislations appear still inadequate to comprise co-cultivation of multiple species in proximity [67]. Hence, there are no general rules and guidance for practitioners, which is one of the main factors for the lack of trust by stakeholders in the field in adopting IMTA on an industrial level. Different culture environments affecting the growth of extractive species lead to various bio-mitigation capacities. As most of the land-based experiments are conducted under controlled conditions, interactions between co-cultured species and their natural physical and ecological environments cannot be well represented [68].

Mediterranean coasts are densely populated and there is a high level of competition for coastal space utilization. Nevertheless, fish and mollusk aquaculture has already been established in the Mediterranean region and in the B-Blue countries therein. Indeed, Eurostat reports that France, Greece and Spain are the top producers of European seabass and seabream (Greece and Spain jointly having 75% and 71% of total EU production of seabass and seabream, respectively) [69]. France and Spain are the top producers of mussels in the EU, with jointly having 63% of total EU production [69]. Therefore, the well-established aquaculture sector offers suitable preconditions for developing large-scale cultivation and the development of IMTA systems.

On the other hand, for each species cultured, different markets exist with different demands, potentials and constraints, all of which add to the likelihood of increasing costs before revenues are generated [70]. However, although the share of aquafarming in Europe has not increased significantly since 2008 and has maintained a constant 20% share of the total fisheries production, its production value has doubled and represents 41% of the total value of the EU's total production of fishery products in 2017 [69]. This share can even be dramatically increased if implementing IMTA practices, considering their potential ecological efficiency drive, environmental acceptability, product-diversity, profitability and benefit for society [71]. In a more long-term perspective, IMTA has the potential to provide ecosystem services and benefits not only at the farm level but rather at broader environmental and societal levels. Additionally, the consumer awareness should not be excluded in the case of IMTA. Along the seafood value chain, the way Mediterranean aquaculture economies are organized may change, with consumers asking for sustainably farmed seafood from traceable and transparent sources, and aquaculture offering "on-demand" sustainable products from selective and safe farms.

An interesting fact also emerges in the IMTA potential in the Mediterranean region. We argued in the beginning of the article that one of the main bottlenecks of advancing in marine biotechnology is the fragmentation of knowledge and businesses. To advance in the technology readiness of any of the selected value chains, there is therefore a need for transdisciplinary and transnational collaborations. This is true when establishing IMTA practices, but only initially. Initially, there is a need to ensure the integration between the

separate companies at an operational level in order to deal with different production cycles, processing the different components of the IMTA system and the availability of infrastructure. The next level demands the fragmentation of activities to find markets and distribution networks for the additional extractive organisms. This is well encompassed in the context of industrial symbiosis, a process where waste/by-products from one industrial level represent resources for the next industrial process. IMTA can be well incorporated into the industrial symbiosis concept, which establishes a collaborative web of knowledge, businesses, material and energy exchanges among different players in the industrial symbiosis networks [72]. Industrial symbiosis demands collaborations offered by geographic proximity [73]. This concept is therefore of high relevance to increase the economic prosperity of Mediterranean countries as the business opportunities diversify and multiply by creating additional value chains through IMTA.

3.2.3. Aquaculture/fisheries/processing by-products Category 3, discards and bycatch valorization in added value sectors

Discards, or discarded catch, include target species or any other species that constitute a part of the catch during fishing operations but are not retained on board and are returned at sea dead or alive [74]. In the Mediterranean bottom trawl fisheries, the discard rate is estimated at 13.3-26.8%, with an average of 18.6% [75,76]. The mitigation of discards is a major concern to conservation bodies and the wider public, as discards are linked to mortality of juvenile fishes, benthic species and biodiversity loss [77]. Bycatch refers to species, with or without commercial value, that are not targeted by the fishery [74]. It is estimated that bycatch represents around 40% of global marine catches [75]. Finally, the by-products result from the processing of fishery and aquaculture products in the commercial and processing chain, including gutting, scaling, skinning, filleting, gill removal and head removal. The by-products (e.g., heads, bones, guts, shells, among others) represent between 30-70% of the whole fish and often go unutilized, ending up as waste [78]. The estimations for discards and by-products for the eight Mediterranean countries are provided in Tables 1 and 2, respectively and amount to the range between 1,069,422 and 2,142,859 tons yearly. These wastes represent a major ecological and economical issue [79]. On the other side, they are also an opportunity, where a promising solution is their valorization as raw materials for production of high added-value compounds in the pharmaceutical, feed, food, energy, cosmetic industry, and agriculture, instead of being discarded [80,81]. Fishery and aquaculture wastes are indeed extremely rich in high-quality compounds (such as proteins having different biological properties), leading to a great potential for the bioprocess industry to exploit these highly valuable products. Indeed, landfilling along other municipal waste is the last option and should not be considered as a valorization option [81]. It is projected that large amounts of new fish biomass will be generated in European ports following the Landing Obligation Guidelines issued by the EU [82,83]. Despite having several good practices in Northern Europe [80,81], aquaculture/fisheries/processing by-products, unavoidable/unwanted catches and discards in the Mediterranean Sea are currently without doubt an underutilized sector.

Table 1. Average capture production statistics between 2014 and 2018 for eight Mediterranean countries. Data taken from the Food and Agriculture (FAO) Fisheries and Aquaculture statistics database. The discard rate was calculated based on published estimations for the Mediterranean Sea (average of 18.6%) [76].

Country	Average capture production 2010-2019 [tons]	Estimated discard rate (13.3-26.8%) [tons]
Croatia	Fish: 70,709	Total: 9,781-19,709
	Mollusks: 1,864	
	Crustaceans: 967	
	Total: 73,540	
France	Fish: 426,078	
	Mollusks: 74,750	
	Crustaceans: 15,885	

	Total: 516,714	Total: 68,723-138,479
Greece	Fish: 58,386 Mollusks: 6,947 Crustaceans: 6,182 Total: 71,515	Total: 9,511-19,166
Italy	Fish: 134,790 Mollusks: 39,621 Crustaceans: 21,325 Total: 195,735	Total: 26,033-52,457
Montenegro	Fish: 1,209 Mollusks: 158 Crustaceans: 34 Total: 1,401	Total: 186-375
Portugal	Fish: 163,173 Mollusks: 17,597 Crustaceans: 1,528 Total: 182,298	Total: 24,246-48,856
Slovenia	Fish: 288 Mollusks: 31 Crustaceans: 3 Total: 322	Total: 43-86
Spain	Fish: 897,491 Mollusks: 51,996 Crustaceans: 15,255 Total: 964,743	Total: 128,311-258,551
TOTAL for 8 Mediterranean countries	Fish: 1,752,125 Mollusks: 192,964 Crustaceans: 61,178 Total: 2,006,267	Total: 266,833-537,680

Table 2. Average annual apparent seafood consumption between 2014 and 2018 and estimation of fish by-products category 3 from the processing of fish from fishery and aquaculture in the retail, commercial and processing chain. Data was calculated using the formula *Average apparent seafood consumption = Fisheries production (Table 1) + Aquaculture production + Imports - Exports* (Supplementary File 1 and tables therein). The by-products amounts were calculated based on conservative estimations for the Mediterranean region (15-30%).

Country	Average yearly apparent seafood consumption 2014-2018 [tons]	Estimated by-products (15-30%) [tons]
Croatia	85,163	12,774-25,549
France	1,476,484	221,473-442,945
Greece	270,308	40,546-81,092
Italy	1,272,150	190,823-381,645
Montenegro	6,075	911-1,822
Portugal	429,799	64,670-128,940
Slovenia	14,852	2,228-4,455
Spain	1,795,766	269,365-538,730
TOTAL for 8 Mediterranean countries	5,350,596	802,589-1,605,179

3.2.4. Identified specific bottlenecks for promising Mediterranean value chains

Besides the general bottlenecks that are preventing the advancement of marine biotechnology activities in the Mediterranean region, discussed in Step 1: Analysis, specific bottlenecks have been identified for each of the three promising value chains (Figure 6). These have been identified through rounds of consultations during B-Blue activities – workshops, trainings, work cafés, networking events, hackathons and strategic meetings. Importantly, the list of the specific bottlenecks is a living document, drafted as a result of

direct interactions by B-Blue stakeholders. The bottlenecks might change over time, depending on the financial, research, regulatory and time efforts spent to develop the three value chains.

605
606
607

SPECIFIC	GENERAL		
	ALGAE	IMTA	WASTE VALORIZATION
Continuous R&D	X	X	X
Infrastructure	X	X	X
Market research	X	X	X
Pilot plants / sites	X	X	
Material availability			X
Consumer awareness		X	X
Technological maturity		X	
Licensing	X	X	

608

Figure 6. General bottlenecks to advance in marine biotechnology in the Mediterranean region (top of the figure) and specific bottlenecks that were identified for three promising value chains for the region. The identification of bottlenecks was done as a combination of project expert opinions (to define the general bottlenecks – in the step 1: analysis/setting the scene part of the B-Blue project activities) and expert stakeholder opinions that were collected during project activities (as described in the Materials and methods section).

609
610
611
612
613
614

Concerning the development of algae production, there is a need to improve data quality and additional research, knowledge sharing and collective action to expand cultivation beyond the currently limited commercial species. Cooperation among stakeholders, collaboration with producers and research institutions should be integrated into R&D to define good practices and introduce cost-effective technologies for algal producers. To optimize the time efficiency and cost-effectiveness of production of algal biomass and compound, further market research is needed to understand the opportunities of the sector in the Mediterranean region. This can lead to proposing strategies to manage social and economic risks. Importantly, standardization of biomass production, licensing framework and licensing procedures are needed, as they can affect processing and production capabilities. Current processing technologies allow obtaining a large portfolio of products for largely different applications. However, to increase the relevance of algal sector, new end products must be targeted, which requires the development of new processing technologies. Additionally, import of products with misleading labelling and abiding to specific EU/national directives (e.g., irradiation, heavy metals, etc.) is an issue that has to be properly addressed. In terms of licensing and patenting, these steps may significantly delay the time to market due to the lengthy compliance processes on one hand, and the patent regulation obstacles on the other, considering also that patent protection is time limited and has to be renewed after several years [84]. Moreover, patent subjects cannot be published until the patent is approved and even after the patent is granted, the protection

615
616
617
618
619
620
621
622
623
624
625
626
627
628
629
630
631
632
633
634

is territory and time limited [84]. Finally, adequate infrastructure is needed for algae production. This will not be feasible without public incentives. However, incentives to promote national production are limited, including the quality control of imported biomass, which often represents unfair competition between producers and importers. Interestingly, an opportunity to develop this emerging value chain has resulted as a consequence of Covid-19 pandemic, that is the need to use local resources [85,86]. It is therefore no longer advisable to buy biomass from abroad or even overseas, but rather to use local suppliers. This is also driven by the market and end-users looking for high value-added products. In the Mediterranean region, the extensive coastline offers suitable preconditions for developing large-scale cultivation of algal biomass. Several production technologies have already been piloted, however a bottleneck for economically viable exploitation of macro- and microalgae is an efficient, industrial scale cultivation technology. The establishment of regional pilot plants and small biorefineries could encourage and boost further investments. The expansion of microalgae farming, large on-shore or off-shore seaweed farming and especially innovative applications require extensive support in both capital investment and more likely on short-medium operation until profit sea-margin could be achieved. Few success stories exist worldwide and they all started up with significant access to research and capital credit, either public or public-private partnerships, until they could be financially self-sustainable on their revenues.

To advance the development of IMTA, a continuous research and development is essential to understand the biological, biochemical, hydrographic, oceanographic, seasonal processes; suitable selection of species, considering the warm oligotrophic Mediterranean waters; adaption and development of new technologies; address the engineering, operational protocol, and economics of these technologies; model development flexible and friendly enough so that they can be tailored and adjusted to the specifics of each particular site. There is a scarcity of adequate infrastructures for IMTA production. Hence, the competitiveness with introduced products will not be feasible without public incentives. Moreover, technology should reach maturity and prove economic viability through the demonstration of pilot-scale/demonstration sites before it can be commercially implemented. The results from these demonstrations must be coupled with profound market research. Financial benefits for the aquaculture companies are one of the most important factors to guarantee industrial support and willingness to implement IMTA. In the Mediterranean region that is heavily dependent on tourism, awareness raising campaigns should target the potential consumers and industry to understand environmental benefits and eliminate the stigma of IMTA being a “waste of coastal space”, as was mentioned during the events organized by B-Blue partners. Funding IMTA systems as nature-based solutions for environmental remediation supporting ecosystem goods and services is a challenge. The scalability of IMTA, i.e., the ability to start growing a new species at a small scale before investing lots of time, money, and other resources before the implementation of large-scale infrastructure, demands for testing these systems under several operational workflow combinations before their implementation. Finally, limitations to the implementation of IMTA at commercial scale are derived at the national level of regulations (as being one of the general bottlenecks for advancement of marine biotechnology value chains), coupled with fundamental aspects of authorization and licensing, environmental impact assessment and the co-cultivation of different species.

One of the main challenges for the valorization of discards and fish by-products is the willingness of the fishing industry (fisheries, aquaculture and processing) to maintain continuous R&D for the valorization of discards and by-products in the B-Blue countries. In turn, the scientific sector must increase their efforts to promote effective collaborations with the industrial sector that yield tangible results. Currently however, infrastructures able to handle fish by-products produced by the catching sector are limited. Moreover, there is a need to develop business models. These include the collection, handling, maintenance and transfer of raw material, creation of practical solutions for the separation and proper storage, development/adaptation of protocols for production of added-value compounds. These business models support a circular economy approach with the potential

of connecting blue and green economies. In the broader Mediterranean region, no successful solutions are applied yet, and tons of unexplored biomass end up in the sea or in landfills. One of the main challenges for the valorization of discards and fish by-products is the available quantities for processing in the Mediterranean region: we estimated from slightly over 1 Mt (optimistically low estimation) to slightly over 2.1 Mt of discards and by-products yearly in the eight Mediterranean countries (Tables 1 and 2). The complex logistics behind novel supply chains needs to be developed to collect and distribute these wastes so they are available for further processing. The final identified bottleneck that prevents the implementation of waste valorization value chains in the Mediterranean region was identified as the necessity to raise awareness and change the perception on waste as a resource in the eyes of consumers as well as fishermen and aquaculture experts. Indeed, any solution for the valorization of waste must involve the local fisheries communities that should be educated and trained for the environmental and financial viability of such initiatives.

3.3. Step 3: Capitalization – creation of national Mediterranean blue biotechnology hubs

The creation of national Mediterranean blue biotechnology hubs enabled to address the state of the art on the national level, analyze encountered challenges and opportunities, anticipate emerging issues, identify bottlenecks for development and needs/priorities for the different stages of the value chain to advance the innovation potential in the Mediterranean region. Moreover, the identified stakeholders from the stakeholder mapping (from scientific, academic, industrial, governmental and other public or nongovernmental sectors) were contacted and had the opportunity to promote themselves, their expertise and their potential involvement in the identified value chains with most potential. The non-technical development of value chains consisted of several activities. Almost 40 activities were organized within the B-Blue project, which attracted over 1,500 participants. This high interest in marine biotechnology strongly suggests the need for networking opportunities in the Mediterranean region to advance the innovation potential. The selection of activities depended on the local context and state of development of the value chain within each blue biotechnology hub. The activities conducted (national workshops, work cafés, networking events, technical workshops, hackathons, and strategic meetings) are detailed in the Materials and Methods section. Importantly, the establishment of blue biotechnology hubs enables the creation of localized resource and activity centers. This can effectively result in setting up new collaborative agendas for research and development that will help finalize the technology readiness levels, form regulatory guidelines, advocate for policy change, put on market new products and processes, contribute to local economy, and thus increase the innovation level in the Mediterranean region. However, any such activities demand follow-up actions and resources (so-called “backbone funding”) to support their basic organizational operations, make concrete plans, assign roles and secure their sustainability [87,88].

Ideally, we would propose a form of sustainability or formalization of these national blue biotechnology hubs through securing national and international funds or capitalizing them in forms of spin offs or creation of professional clusters. When these clusters are integrated into new or existing international ones, it is however important to maintain their regional independence to some extent as regionalization of innovation policy more accurately considers the regional specific context and circumstances in terms of the industrial structure, institutional set-up and knowledge base [89]. Such blue biotechnology hubs should be of strategic importance for the Mediterranean region to enable a faster adoption of marine biotechnology and facilitate stakeholders towards a faster development and application of promising value chains without the need to duplicate the efforts and reinvent the wheel for processes which were already initiated but had no possibility to display their good practices or span beyond national borders due to a lack of established blue biotechnology hubs. With the aim of having these hubs to act as national and regional innovation catalysts, we propose a roadmap for development of new marine biotechnology value chains in the Mediterranean region (Figure 7). We propose the process in five

steps, where the first four are essential prerequisites for success and should be implemented even before the actual technical part (in the laboratories or on pilot sites) – step 5. These are the (i) contextual steps (step 1 – benchmark the current sets of good practices that will also enable the identification of key stakeholders and determine possible bottlenecks that limit innovation and the development of marine biotechnology value chains; and step 3 – prepare action plans with newly established collaborative networks by defining roles, responsibilities, main activities and -especially- the main gains in participating in the process) and (ii) strategic steps (step 2 – building the community by implementation of activities that enable the co-creation of knowledge and step 4 – advocacy with important stakeholders to provide financial and legislative support).

Figure 7. Roadmap for activities for development of marine biotechnology value chains in the Mediterranean region.

4. Materials and Methods

To set the scene and enable the identification of background requirements to advance in marine biotechnology, a survey was set. In March 2021, selected experts – B-Blue project partners – from 8 Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain; 1-2 experts per project partner, 14 overall) were enrolled in a survey where respondents were asked to tick “five activities which you consider are most important for advancing marine biotechnology capability building in your country”. A total of 81 potential activities were suggested, originating from suggestions and solutions as outlined by the Blue Bioeconomy Forum [17]. The assumption behind this survey was that any activity that is considered important by several respondents’ points towards an important set of activities for the development of the marine biotechnology sector in the Mediterranean region.

To identify good practices, we used a combination of desktop research to collect and systematize the existing knowledge, allowing to identify the local innovators. We define the existing knowledge as “good practices”. These may refer to standards, regulations, methods, and procedures that are applied and can be followed to build a resource-efficient society and promote the SDGs. In addition, a good practice can be considered an implemented, ready to market project or/and a pilot action/research project with actual results. To benchmark the good practices in the Mediterranean countries that participated in this project (Supplementary Table 1), each partner assembled the data on individual good practices, including: the organization behind the development of a best practice, funding source, short description of the idea, sector/field (aquaculture, cosmetics, health/pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, feed industry, energy, industrial processes, environment or other). Individual good practices were then categorized (business creation, technology transfer, technology support, funding mechanism, policy management, collaboration and networking, marketing/branding, other). The technology readiness and business levels were also determined.

To create national blue biotechnology hubs, we adopted a collaborative territorial approach to create an appropriate space for the interaction of communities with different knowledge and interests to reach a critical mass for the marine biotechnology sector, to generate innovation and transfer it to the commercialization stage. Initially, a stakeholder

mapping exercise was performed where national country representatives from 8 Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain) mapped individual stakeholders based on their category (Administrative and public bodies, Industry and SMEs, Scientific institutions and academia, NGOs, Media representatives, Past and current projects). Afterwards, each stakeholder was assessed based on their interest and influence level in the field of marine biotechnology. This resulted in creation of stakeholder maps. An example of a stakeholder map is provided in Figure 8. This exercise was done to categorize and tailor the collaboration and engagement with stakeholders. The primary targets were those with high interest and high influence (top right quadrant). Stakeholders that are highly influential but have a low interest in the topic are targeted with activities to raise awareness, inform them and somehow incentivize them to grasp the importance of the topic. On the other hand, stakeholders with a high interest but low influence were used to inform them about our activities and provide a platform for their feedback. Finally, those with low interest and influence (bottom left quadrant) are monitored for their potential changes in either influence or interest in future. Five national blue biotechnology hubs were defined (France, Greece, Italy, Slovenia and Spain) through various activities. (1) The national workshops (a minimum of one in each country) were organized with the aim of raising awareness on the marine biotechnology and blue bioeconomy sectors, summarizing the state-of-the-art, offering a platform for showcasing expertise by participants, network, discuss ideas related to the development of the sector and plan future activities and strategies. (2) Networking events such as work cafés were organized to exchange the opinions and needs of stakeholders, which enabled the definition of future steps towards implementing marine biotechnology value chains. (3) Technical workshops enabled an in-depth discussion on the selected value chains, the identification of potential bottlenecks and provided an opportunity to showcase the individual stakeholders' expertise. (4) Hackathons provided a platform to find specific solutions, identify technological innovations in the maritime field, which can be applied to improve an existing situation or give rise to a new concept. (5) Strategic meetings provided a platform with fewer stakeholders that enabled creating and further reinforcing collaborative associations with the aim of defining participatory actions for further development of the selected value chains. They were also the tool of choice for communication between the five Mediterranean blue biotechnology hubs (France, Greece, Italy, Slovenia and Spain). Throughout these events, the feedback from participants was used to identify to bottlenecks from various stakeholder categories and is also included in the Discussion section.

Figure 8. A stakeholder map example to identify the most relevant stakeholders for advancing the marine biotechnology field. The dots indicate individual stakeholders, and their placement indicated their combined interest and influence in the sector. Based on their positioning in the map, these stakeholders can be invited to form strategic collaborations. Dots are color-coded to represent

their sector (grey – administrative and public bodies; grey/blue – industry and SMEs, blue – scientific institutions and academia; orange – NGOs; yellow – media representatives; green – past and current projects). 828
829
830

5. Conclusions 831

This article assessed the current state of innovation in the marine biotechnology value chains development in the Mediterranean. Focusing on 8 Mediterranean countries (Croatia, Greece, France, Italy, Montenegro, Portugal, Slovenia and Spain), we benchmarked the current good practices to avoid the fragmentation of knowledge and prepare national and international strategies. We have identified the sectors which are of highest potential for the Mediterranean region. Algal production (macro- and microalgae) for added-value products, IMTA and the valorization of fisheries and aquaculture discards, bycatch and by-products could prepare the Mediterranean countries to advance their innovation potential. Through the participatory activities we created the so-called blue biotechnology national hubs, i.e., ecosystems where collaborations, knowledge transfer and spill-over effects can occur to spur innovation and business within the marine biotechnology value chains. Considering that the establishment of a value chain is typically a long process that needs the involvement of technical and non-technical expertise, addressing the legislative framework (either national, regional or international one) with a severe reliance on the precarious nature of science and innovation financing, consolidated efforts are needed to push further the development of value chains with highest potential for development. Their success is not only dictated by the advances in research and development (i.e., technical skills) but, as we have shown, also by maintaining the non-technical operations. These include mutual learning platforms, monitoring, identification and sharing of good practices to build potential synergies, networking, advocacy and involvement with the policy making sector to iterate the legislation and guarantee a more stable funding and further stimulate innovation, better collaboration between the public and private sector stakeholders to stimulate investment and development of value chains, securing funding for maintenance of national blue biotechnology hubs, transfer of knowledge and provision of experts to span beyond the national borders and benefit the whole Mediterranean economy. Such hubs should also build capacity on the market aspects and represent a proxy towards raising consumer awareness and acceptance. Therefore, special focus should be given to incentivize and finance the establishment of national blue biotechnology hubs with an international outreach, where expertise, infrastructure and pilot sites can be shared to advance in the Mediterranean sustainable bioeconomy, thus enabling transformational change, engaging Mediterranean society, making decisions circular and environmentally friendly. 832
833
834
835
836
837
838
839
840
841
842
843
844
845
846
847
848
849
850
851
852
853
854
855
856
857
858
859
860
861
862
863

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: 864
www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Supplementary Table 1: Collection of good marine biotechnology practices 865
by the B-Blue Mediterranean countries; Supplementary File S1: Supporting data on aquaculture pro- 866
duction, imports and exports in the Mediterranean countries. 867

Author Contributions: AR designed the manuscript concept and drafted the manuscript. AG, AV 868
and GT designed-drafted the analysis of the promising value chains in the Mediterranean region. 869
All authors contributed with assessment benchmarking, their specific field of expertise, read, edited 870
and approved the final version of the manuscript. 871

Funding: This publication has been produced with financial assistance of the Interreg MED Pro- 872
gramme, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (Project No. 873
8MED20_4.1_SP_001, internal ref. 8MED20_4.1_SP_001) – B-Blue project. AR, EGB, JU, GT, ER: this 874
publication is based upon work from COST Action CA18238 (Ocean4Biotech), supported by COST 875
(European Cooperation in Science and Technology). AR, EGB, JU: The authors acknowledge the 876
financial support from the Slovenian Research Agency (research core funding No. P4-0432). The 877
authors also acknowledge the project (L4-4564) was financially supported by the Slovenian Research 878
Agency. YK, ER, GT: this publication is based on results from the VIOAXIOPPIO Project funded 879
from the Greek General Secretariat of Research and Innovation (T1EAK-02509 – MIS 5031878). 880

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable. 881

Data Availability Statement: All data produced during this study consisting of interviews and desk research and are not included in this manuscript are presented as project deliverables on the project website (<https://b-blue.interreg-med.eu/>). In case some of the data are not publicly available, interested readers are referred to address their inquiry to the corresponding author (AR).

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to acknowledge Anja Sergaš (National Institute of Biology) for her excellent administrative support, Ioannis Tzovenis (MikroPhycos) and Ioannis Karakassis, Manolis Tsapakis, Nafsika Papageorgiou (Univeristy of Crete and HCMR) for their contribution on algae and IMTA value chains.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

References

1. European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. *Innovating for Sustainable Growth :A Bioeconomy for Europe.*; Publications Office: LU, 2012;
2. Rotter, A.; Bacu, A.; Barbier, M.; Bertoni, F.; Bones, A.M.; Cancela, M.L.; Carlsson, J.; Carvalho, M.F.; Cegłowska, M.; Dalay, M.C.; et al. A New Network for the Advancement of Marine Biotechnology in Europe and Beyond. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **2020**, *7*, 278, doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.00278.
3. Doussineau, Mathieu; Gomez, Javier; Gnamus, Ales; Haarich, Silke; Holstein, Frank *Smart Specialisation and Blue Biotechnology in Europe.*; Publications Office: LU, 2020;
4. European Commission Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions On A New Approach For A Sustainable Blue Economy In The EU Transforming The EU's Blue Economy For A Sustainable Future. COM(2021) 240 Fina. 2021.
5. Haaf, A.; Hofmann, S.; Schüler, J. Measuring the Economic Footprint of the Biotechnology Industry in Europe. *Industrial Biotechnology* **2021**, *17*, 117–124, doi:10.1089/ind.2021.29249.aha.
6. Timmis, K.; de Lorenzo, V.; Verstraete, W.; Ramos, J.L.; Danchin, A.; Brüssow, H.; Singh, B.K.; Timmis, J.K. The Contribution of Microbial Biotechnology to Economic Growth and Employment Creation. *Microb. Biotechnol.* **2017**, *10*, 1137–1144, doi:10.1111/1751-7915.12845.
7. Martín-López, B.; Oteros-Rozas, E.; Cohen-Shacham, E.; Santos-Martín, F.; Nieto-Romero, M.; Carvalho-Santos, C.; González, J.A.; García-Llorente, M.; Klass, K.; Geijzendorffer, I.; et al. Ecosystem Services Supplied by Mediterranean Basin Ecosystems. In *Routledge Handbook of Ecosystem Services*; Potschin, M., Haines-Young, R., Fish, R., Turner, R.K., Eds.; Routledge: New York, NY : Routledge, 2016., 2016; pp. 405–414 ISBN 978-1-315-77530-2.
8. Casini, M.; Bastianoni, S.; Gagliardi, F.; Gigliotti, M.; Riccaboni, A.; Betti, G. Sustainable Development Goals Indicators: A Methodological Proposal for a Multidimensional Fuzzy Index in the Mediterranean Area. *Sustainability* **2019**, *11*, 1198, doi:10.3390/su11041198.
9. Coll, M.; Piroddi, C.; Steenbeek, J.; Kaschner, K.; Ben Rais Lasram, F.; Aguzzi, J.; Ballesteros, E.; Bianchi, C.N.; Corbera, J.; Dailianis, T.; et al. The Biodiversity of the Mediterranean Sea: Estimates, Patterns, and Threats. *PLOS ONE* **2010**, *5*, 1–36, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0011842.
10. Gedikli, A.; Derindağ, M. Innovation, Macroeconomic Effects, and Environmental Degradation: The Case of Mediterranean Countries. In *Management and Conservation of Mediterranean Environments*; Castanho, Rui Alexandre, Gallardo, José Martín, Eds.; IGI Global: Pennsylvania, USA, 2021; pp. 134–158 ISBN 978-1-79987-393-8.
11. Ronchi, F.; Galgani, F.; Binda, F.; Mandić, M.; Peterlin, M.; Tutman, P.; Anastasopoulou, A.; Fortibuoni, T. Fishing for Litter in the Adriatic-Ionian Macroregion (Mediterranean Sea): Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats. *Marine Policy* **2019**, *100*, 226–237, doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.11.041.

12. Rotter, A.; Gaudêncio, S.P.; Klun, K.; Macher, J.-N.; Thomas, O.P.; Deniz, I.; Edwards, C.; Grigalionyte-Bembič, E.; Ljubešić, Z.; Robbens, J.; et al. A New Tool for Faster Construction of Marine Biotechnology Collaborative Networks. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **2021**, *8*, 530, doi:10.3389/fmars.2021.685164.
13. Rotter, A.; Barbier, M.; Bertoni, F.; Bones, A.M.; Cancela, M.L.; Carlsson, J.; Carvalho, M.F.; Ceglowska, M.; Chirivella-Martorell, J.; Conk Dalay, M.; et al. The Essentials of Marine Biotechnology. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **2021**, *8*, 158, doi:10.3389/fmars.2021.629629.
14. Fernández-Macías, E.; Hurley, J.; Peruffo, E.; Storrie, D.W.; Poel, M.; Packalén, E. *Game Changing Technologies: Exploring the Impact on Production Processes and Work*; Research report / Eurofound; Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 2018; ISBN 978-92-897-1628-4.
15. Kaplinsky, R.; Morris, M. *A Handbook for Value Chain Research (Vol. 113)*; University of Sussex, Institute of Development Studies: Brighton, UK, 2000, pp. 4-8.
16. Collins, J.E.; Vanagt, T.; Huys, I.; Vieira, H. Marine Bioresource Development – Stakeholder’s Challenges, Implementable Actions, and Business Models. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **2020**, *7*, 62, doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.00062.
17. Executive Agency for Small and Medium sized Enterprises.; Technopolis Group.; Wageningen Research. *Blue Bioeconomy Forum. Highlights: Synthesis of the Roadmap and a Selection of Viable and Innovative Projects.*; Publications Office: LU, 2020;
18. Hossain, M.; Leminen, S.; Westerlund, M. A Systematic Review of Living Lab Literature. *Journal of Cleaner Production* **2019**, *213*, 976–988, doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.257.
19. European Commission *The EU Blue Economy Report. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg., 2021.*; Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 2021;
20. Ribera d’Alcalà, M.; Buongiorno Nardelli, B.; Sprovieri, M.; Cappelletto, M. *The BLUEMED Italian White Paper. An Overview of Relevance, Obstacles and Proposals of the Key Sectors for a Blue Growth*; Zenodo, 2018;
21. Farmery, A.K.; Allison, E.H.; Andrew, N.L.; Troell, M.; Voyer, M.; Campbell, B.; Eriksson, H.; Fabinyi, M.; Song, A.M.; Steenbergen, D. Blind Spots in Visions of a “Blue Economy” Could Undermine the Ocean’s Contribution to Eliminating Hunger and Malnutrition. *One Earth* **2021**, *4*, 28–38, doi:10.1016/j.oneear.2020.12.002.
22. Stentiford, G.D.; Bateman, I.J.; Hinchliffe, S.J.; Bass, D.; Hartnell, R.; Santos, E.M.; Devlin, M.J.; Feist, S.W.; Taylor, N.G.H.; Verner-Jeffreys, D.W.; et al. Sustainable Aquaculture through the One Health Lens. *Nat Food* **2020**, *1*, 468–474, doi:10.1038/s43016-020-0127-5.
23. Capello, R.; Kroll, H. From Theory to Practice in Smart Specialization Strategy: Emerging Limits and Possible Future Trajectories. *European Planning Studies* **2016**, *24*, 1393–1406, doi:10.1080/09654313.2016.1156058.
24. Asheim, B.; Grillitsch, M.; Tripl, M. Chapter 4 - Smart Specialization as an Innovation-Driven Strategy for Economic Diversification: Examples From Scandinavian Regions. In *Advances in the Theory and Practice of Smart Specialization*; Radosevic, S., Curaj, A., Gheorghiu, R., Andreescu, L., Wade, I., Eds.; Academic Press, 2017; pp. 73–97 ISBN 978-0-12-804137-6.
25. Ruhrmann, H.; Fritsch, M.; Leydesdorff, L. Synergy and Policy-Making in German Innovation Systems: Smart Specialisation Strategies at National, Regional, Local Levels? *Regional Studies* **2022**, *56*, 1468–1479, doi:10.1080/00343404.2021.1872780.
26. Anderson, D.R. The Importance of Mentoring Programs to Women’s Career Advancement in Biotechnology. *Journal of Career Development* **2005**, *32*, 60–73, doi:10.1177/0894845305277039.
27. Comi, S.; Resmini, L. Are Export Promotion Programs Effective in Promoting the Internalization of SMEs? *Econ Polit* **2020**, *37*, 547–581, doi:10.1007/s40888-019-00170-8.
28. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations FAO Yearbook. Fishery and Aquaculture Statistics 2019*; FAO, 2021; ISBN 978-92-5-135410-0.

29. Visch, W.; Kononets, M.; Hall, P.O.J.; Nylund, G.M.; Pavia, H. Environmental Impact of Kelp (*Saccharina Latissima*) Aquaculture. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **2020**, *155*, 110962, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2020.110962>. 969
970
30. Damanaki, Maria; Vincent, Adrien; Bucher, Maximilian *Hidden Champion of the Ocean: Seaweed as a Growth Engine for a Sustainable European Future*; Seaweed for Europe, 2020; 971
972
31. Filbee-Dexter, K.; Wernberg, T.; Barreiro, R.; Coleman, M.A.; de Bettignies, T.; Feehan, C.J.; Franco, J.N.; Hasler, B.; Louro, I.; Norderhaug, K.M.; et al. Leveraging the Blue Economy to Transform Marine Forest Restoration. *Journal of Phycology* **2022**, *58*, 198–207, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jpy.13239>. 973
974
975
32. Silva, C.O.; Lemos, M.F.L.; Gaspar, R.; Gonçalves, C.; Neto, J.M. The Effects of the Invasive Seaweed *Asparagopsis armata* on Native Rock Pool Communities: Evidences from Experimental Exclusion. *Ecological Indicators* **2021**, *125*, 107463, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.107463>. 976
977
978
33. View Data | EMODnet Human Activities Available online: <https://www.emodnet-humanactivities.eu/view-data.php> (accessed on 5 January 2023). 979
980
34. Morais, M.G. de; Vaz, B. da S.; Morais, E.G. de; Costa, J.A.V. Biological Effects of *Spirulina* (*Arthrospira*) Biopolymers and Biomass in the Development of Nanostructured Scaffolds. *BioMed Research International* **2014**, *2014*, 1–9, doi:10.1155/2014/762705. 981
982
983
35. Sili, C.; Torzillo, G.; Vonshak, A. *Arthrospira* (Spirulina). In *Ecology of Cyanobacteria II*; Whitton, B.A., Ed.; Springer Netherlands: Dordrecht, 2012; pp. 677–705 ISBN 978-94-007-3854-6. 984
985
36. Barbier, M.; Charrier, B. PEGASUS : PHYCORMORPH EUROPEAN GUIDELINES FOR A SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE OF SEaweEDS., doi:10.21411/2C3W-YC73. 986
987
37. MacArtain, P.; Gill, C.I.R.; Brooks, M.; Campbell, R.; Rowland, I.R. Nutritional Value of Edible Seaweeds. *Nutrition Reviews* **2008**, *65*, 535–543, doi:10.1111/j.1753-4887.2007.tb00278.x. 988
989
38. Cherry, P.; Yadav, S.; Strain, C.R.; Allsopp, P.J.; McSorley, E.M.; Ross, R.P.; Stanton, C. Prebiotics from Seaweeds: An Ocean of Opportunity? *Marine Drugs* **2019**, *17*, 327, doi:10.3390/md17060327. 990
991
39. Araújo, R.; Vázquez Calderón, F.; Sánchez López, J.; Azevedo, I.C.; Bruhn, A.; Fluch, S.; Garcia Tasende, M.; Ghaderiardakani, F.; Ilmjärv, T.; Laurans, M.; et al. Current Status of the Algae Production Industry in Europe: An Emerging Sector of the Blue Bioeconomy. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **2021**, *7*, 626389, doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.626389. 992
993
994
40. Hasselström, L.; Visch, W.; Gröndahl, F.; Nylund, G.M.; Pavia, H. The Impact of Seaweed Cultivation on Ecosystem Services - a Case Study from the West Coast of Sweden. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **2018**, *133*, 53–64, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2018.05.005>. 995
996
997
41. Mac Monagail, M.; Cornish, L.; Morrison, L.; Araújo, R.; Critchley, A.T. Sustainable Harvesting of Wild Seaweed Resources. *European Journal of Phycology* **2017**, *52*, 371–390, doi:10.1080/09670262.2017.1365273. 998
999
42. European Commission. Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries.; EUMOFA. *Blue Bio-Economy: Situation Report and Perspectives.*; Publications Office: LU, 2018; 1000
1001
43. Buschmann, A.H.; Camus, C.; Infante, J.; Neori, A.; Israel, Á.; Hernández-González, M.C.; Pereda, S.V.; Gomez-Pinchetti, J.L.; Golberg, A.; Tadmor-Shalev, N.; et al. Seaweed Production: Overview of the Global State of Exploitation, Farming and Emerging Research Activity. *European Journal of Phycology* **2017**, *52*, 391–406, doi:10.1080/09670262.2017.1365175. 1002
1003
1004
1005
44. U.S. Food and Drug administration Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) | FDA Available online: <https://www.fda.gov/food/food-ingredients-packaging/generally-recognized-safe-gras> (accessed on 5 January 2023). 1006
1007
45. Nagappan, S.; Das, P.; AbdulQuadir, M.; Thaher, M.; Khan, S.; Mahata, C.; Al-Jabri, H.; Vatland, A.K.; Kumar, G. Potential of Microalgae as a Sustainable Feed Ingredient for Aquaculture. *Journal of Biotechnology* **2021**, *341*, 1–20, doi:10.1016/j.jbiotec.2021.09.003. 1008
1009
1010

46. Madeira, M.S.; Cardoso, C.; Lopes, P.A.; Coelho, D.; Afonso, C.; Bandarra, N.M.; Prates, J.A.M. Microalgae as Feed Ingredients for Livestock Production and Meat Quality: A Review. *Livestock Science* **2017**, *205*, 111–121, doi:10.1016/j.livsci.2017.09.020.
47. Galafat, A.; Vizcaíno, A.J.; Sáez, M.I.; Martínez, T.F.; Arizcun, M.; Chaves-Pozo, E.; Alarcón, F.J. Assessment of Dietary Inclusion of Crude or Hydrolysed *Arthrospira Platensis* Biomass in Starter Diets for Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus Aurata*). *Aquaculture* **2022**, *548*, 737680, doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737680.
48. Mutanda, T.; Naidoo, D.; Bwapwa, J.K.; Anandraj, A. Biotechnological Applications of Microalgal Oleaginous Compounds: Current Trends on Microalgal Bioprocessing of Products. *Front. Energy Res.* **2020**, *8*, 598803, doi:10.3389/fenrg.2020.598803.
49. Koyande, A.K.; Chew, K.W.; Rambabu, K.; Tao, Y.; Chu, D.-T.; Show, P.-L. Microalgae: A Potential Alternative to Health Supplementation for Humans. *Food Science and Human Wellness* **2019**, *8*, 16–24, doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fshw.2019.03.001.
50. Barbosa, M.J.; Janssen, M.; Südfeld, C.; D’Adamo, S.; Wijffels, R.H. Hypes, Hopes, and the Way Forward for Microalgal Biotechnology. *Trends in Biotechnology* **2023**, *41*, 452–471, doi:10.1016/j.tibtech.2022.12.017.
51. Wijffels, R.H. Potential of Sponges and Microalgae for Marine Biotechnology. *Trends in Biotechnology* **2008**, *26*, 26–31, doi:10.1016/j.tibtech.2007.10.002.
52. Narala, R.R.; Garg, S.; Sharma, K.K.; Thomas-Hall, S.R.; Deme, M.; Li, Y.; Schenk, P.M. Comparison of Microalgae Cultivation in Photobioreactor, Open Raceway Pond, and a Two-Stage Hybrid System. *Front. Energy Res.* **2016**, *4*, doi:10.3389/fenrg.2016.00029.
53. Acien, F.G.; Molina, E.; Reis, A.; Torzillo, G.; Zittelli, G.C.; Sepúlveda, C.; Masojídek, J. 1 - Photobioreactors for the Production of Microalgae. In *Microalgae-Based Biofuels and Bioproducts*; Gonzalez-Fernandez, C., Muñoz, R., Eds.; Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy; Woodhead Publishing, 2017; pp. 1–44 ISBN 978-0-08-101023-5.
54. Mayers, J.J.; Ekman Nilsson, A.; Svensson, E.; Albers, E. Integrating Microalgal Production with Industrial Outputs—Reducing Process Inputs and Quantifying the Benefits. *Industrial Biotechnology* **2016**, *12*, 219–234, doi:10.1089/ind.2016.0006.
55. Costa, J.A.V.; Freitas, B.C.B.; Santos, T.D.; Mitchell, B.G.; Morais, M.G. Open Pond System for Microalgae Culture. In Biomass. In *Biofuels and Biochemicals, Biofuels from Algae*; Pandey, A., Chang, J.-S., Soccol, C.R., Lee, D.J., Chist, Y., Eds.; Amsterdam, the Netherlands, 2019.
56. Benedetti, M.; Vecchi, V.; Barera, S.; Dall’Osto, L. Biomass from Microalgae: The Potential of Domestication towards Sustainable Biofactories. *Microb Cell Fact* **2018**, *17*, 173, doi:10.1186/s12934-018-1019-3.
57. Carballeira Braña, C.B.; Cerbule, K.; Senff, P.; Stolz, I.K. Towards Environmental Sustainability in Marine Finfish Aquaculture. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **2021**, *8*, 666662, doi:10.3389/fmars.2021.666662.
58. Naylor, R.L.; Goldberg, R.J.; Primavera, J.H.; Kautsky, N.; Beveridge, M.C.M.; Clay, J.; Folke, C.; Lubchenco, J.; Mooney, H.; Troell, M. Effect of Aquaculture on World Fish Supplies. *Nature* **2000**, *405*, 1017–1024, doi:10.1038/35016500.
59. Troell, M.; Joyce, A.; Chopin, T.; Neori, A.; Buschmann, A.H.; Fang, J.-G. Ecological Engineering in Aquaculture – Potential for Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) in Marine Offshore Systems. *Aquaculture* **2009**, *297*, 1–9, doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2009.09.010.
60. Correia, M.; Azevedo, I.C.; Peres, H.; Magalhães, R.; Oliva-Teles, A.; Almeida, C.M.R.; Guimarães, L. Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture: A Laboratory and Hands-on Experimental Activity to Promote Environmental Sustainability Awareness and Value of Aquaculture Products. *Front. Mar. Sci.* **2020**, *7*, 156, doi:10.3389/fmars.2020.00156.
61. Barrington, K.; Chopin, T.; Robinson, S.; Soto, D. Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) in Marine Temperate Waters. In *Integrated mariculture: a global review*; FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Technical Paper. No. 592; Rome, Italy, 2009; pp. 7–46.

62. Giangrande, A.; Pierrri, C.; Arduini, D.; Borghese, J.; Licciano, M.; Trani, R.; Corriero, G.; Basile, G.; Cecere, E.; Petrocelli, A.; et al. An Innovative IMTA System: Polychaetes, Sponges and Macroalgae Co-Cultured in a Southern Italian In-Shore Mariculture Plant (Ionian Sea). *JMSE* **2020**, *8*, 733, doi:10.3390/jmse8100733.
63. Quintã, R.; Santos, R.; Thomas, D.N.; Le Vay, L. Growth and Nitrogen Uptake by *Salicornia Europaea* and *Aster Tripolium* in Nutrient Conditions Typical of Aquaculture Wastewater. *Chemosphere* **2015**, *120*, 414–421, doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.08.017.
64. Grosso, L.; Rakaj, A.; Fianchini, A.; Morroni, L.; Cataudella, S.; Scardi, M. Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) System Combining the Sea Urchin *Paracentrotus Lividus*, as Primary Species, and the Sea Cucumber *Holothuria Tubulosa* as Extractive Species. *Aquaculture* **2021**, *534*, 736268, doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736268.
65. Chopin, T. Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-Trophic (IMTA) Aquaculture. In *Sustainable Food Production*; Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A., Eds.; Springer New York: New York, NY, 2013; pp. 184–205 ISBN 978-1-4614-5797-8.
66. *Food from the Oceans: How Can More Food and Biomass Be Obtained from the Oceans in a Way That Does Not Deprive Future Generations of Their Benefits?*; Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 2017; ISBN 978-92-79-67730-4.
67. Rosa, J.; Lemos, M.F.L.; Crespo, D.; Nunes, M.; Freitas, A.; Ramos, F.; Pardal, M.Â.; Leston, S. Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture Systems – Potential Risks for Food Safety. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* **2020**, *96*, 79–90, doi:10.1016/j.tifs.2019.12.008.
68. Zhang, J.; Zhang, S.; Kitazawa, D.; Zhou, J.; Park, S.; Gao, S.; Shen, Y. Bio Mitigation Based on Integrated Multi Trophic Aquaculture in Temperate Coastal Waters: Practice, Assessment, and Challenges. *LAJAR* **2019**, *47*, 212–223, doi:10.3856/vol47-issue2-fulltext-1.
69. Aquaculture in the EU - Products Eurostat News - Eurostat Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20191015-2> (accessed on 5 January 2023).
70. Hughes, A.D.. Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture in Europe: Will It Work for Us? *Aquaculture Europe* **2016**, 5–11.
71. Kleitou, P.; Kletou, D.; David, J. Is Europe Ready for Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture? A Survey on the Perspectives of European Farmers and Scientists with IMTA Experience. *Aquaculture* **2018**, *490*, 136–148, doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2018.02.035.
72. Domenech, T.; Davies, M. Structure and Morphology of Industrial Symbiosis Networks: The Case of Kalundborg. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* **2011**, *10*, 79–89, doi:10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.01.011.
73. Chertow, M.R. Industrial Symbiosis: Literature and Taxonomy. *Annu. Rev. Energy. Environ.* **2000**, *25*, 313–337, doi:10.1146/annurev.energy.25.1.313.
74. GFCM. GFCM Data Collection Reference Framework (DCRF). Version 22.1. 2018.
75. Davies, R.W.D.; Cripps, S.J.; Nickson, A.; Porter, G. Defining and Estimating Global Marine Fisheries Bycatch. *Marine Policy* **2009**, *33*, 661–672, doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2009.01.003.
76. Tsagarakis, K.; Pali Alexis, A.; Vassilopoulou, V. Mediterranean Fishery Discards: Review of the Existing Knowledge. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* **2014**, *71*, 1219–1234, doi:10.1093/icesjms/fst074.
77. Stithou, M.; Vassilopoulou, V.; Tsagarakis, K.; Edridge, A.; Machias, A.; Maniopoulou, M.; Dogrammatzi, A.; Bellido, J.; Carbonara, P.; Carbonell, A.; et al. Discarding in Mediterranean Trawl Fisheries—a Review of Potential Measures and Stakeholder Insights. *Maritime Studies* **2019**, *18*, doi:10.1007/s40152-018-00131-0.
78. Fish By-Products Utilization, Getting More Benefits From Fish Processing | Food Loss and Waste in Fish Value Chains | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Available online: <https://www.fao.org/flw-in-fish-value-chains/resources/articles/fish-by-products-utilization-getting-more-benefits-from-fish-processing/en/> (accessed on 5 January 2023).

79. Borges, L. The Evolution of a Discard Policy in Europe. *Fish Fish* **2015**, *16*, 534–540, doi:10.1111/faf.12062. 1098
80. Rudovica, V.; Rotter, A.; Gaudêncio, S.P.; Novoveská, L.; Akgül, F.; Akslen-Hoel, L.K.; Alexandrino, D.A.M.; Anne, O.; Arbidans, L.; Atanassova, M.; et al. Valorization of Marine Waste: Use of Industrial By-Products and Beach Wrack Towards the Production of High Added-Value Products. *Frontiers in Marine Science* **2021**, *8*, 1350, doi:10.3389/fmars.2021.723333. 1099
1100
1101
1102
81. Iñarra, B.; Larsen, E.; Viðarsson, J.E. D6.5 Validation of Final Solution(s) for Best Use of Unavoidable Unwanted Catches; DiscardLess; 1103
1104
82. Venugopal, V. Valorization of Seafood Processing Discards: Bioconversion and Bio-Refinery Approaches. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* **2021**, *5*, 611835, doi:10.3389/fsufs.2021.611835. 1105
1106
83. *The European Landing Obligation: Reducing Discards in Complex, Multi-Species and Multi-Jurisdictional Fisheries*; Uhlmann, S.S., Ulrich, C., Kennelly, S.J., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2019; ISBN 978-3-030-03307-1. 1107
1108
84. Patents Available online: <https://www.wipo.int/patents/en/> (accessed on 29 March 2023). 1109
85. Nemes, G.; Chiffolleau, Y.; Zollet, S.; Collison, M.; Benedek, Z.; Colantuono, F.; Dulrud, A.; Fiore, M.; Holtkamp, C.; Kim, T.-Y.; et al. The Impact of COVID-19 on Alternative and Local Food Systems and the Potential for the Sustainability Transition: Insights from 13 Countries. *Sustainable Production and Consumption* **2021**, *28*, 591–599, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.06.022>. 1110
1111
1112
1113
86. Fava, N.; Laganà, V.R.; Nicolosi, A. The Impact of COVID-19 on Municipal Food Markets: Resilience or Innovative Attitude? *JOItmC* **2022**, *8*, 87, doi:10.3390/joitmc8020087. 1114
1115
87. Yarime, M.; Trencher, G.; Mino, T.; Scholz, R.W.; Olsson, L.; Ness, B.; Frantzeskaki, N.; Rotmans, J. Establishing Sustainability Science in Higher Education Institutions: Towards an Integration of Academic Development, Institutionalization, and Stakeholder Collaborations. *Sustain Sci* **2012**, *7*, 101–113, doi:10.1007/s11625-012-0157-5. 1116
1117
1118
88. Towe, V.L.; Leviton, L.; Chandra, A.; Sloan, J.C.; Tait, M.; Orleans, T. Cross-Sector Collaborations And Partnerships: Essential Ingredients To Help Shape Health And Well-Being. *Health Affairs* **2016**, *35*, 1964–1969, doi:10.1377/hlthaff.2016.0604. 1119
1120
1121
89. Asheim, B.T.; Coenen, L. Knowledge Bases and Regional Innovation Systems: Comparing Nordic Clusters. *Research Policy* **2005**, *34*, 1173–1190, doi:10.1016/j.respol.2005.03.013. 1122
1123
1124